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MANAGEMENT

WORKFORCE DIVERSITY: A CONTRIBUTION TO EMPLOYEES' PERFORMANCE IN STATE UNIVERSITIES IN CAMEROON**Neba Noela Buwah***buwahnoelaneba@gmail.com*

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Abstract

Diversity has been said to be the spice of life. The objective of this study was to investigate the influence of workforce diversity management on employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon. The causal and case study research design was adopted and primary data collected using questionnaire from 260 administrators from both university of Buea and Bamenda in Cameroon. A purposive sampling technique was used and data was analysed using the multiple linear regression model. The results indicated that Age diversity and Government policy have a positive and significant relationship on employees' performance while Ethnic diversity has a negative but positive significance on employee performance and Gender diversity on the other hand has a negative and an insignificant relationship on employees' performance. The study recommended that, the Ministry of Higher Education should set up a supervisory organ that quarterly evaluates the extent to which each university meets the diversity goals. The Universities should be rated in line with prescribed standards and those that have shut fall be punished by reducing their state subventions. And that policy should be implemented to foster the diversity (age and ethnic diversity) culture within state institutions like the university of Buea and Bamenda and discourage all forms of gender bias and discriminations in order to foster a community spirit.

Keywords: *gender diversity, ethnic diversity, age diversity, government policy, employees' performance, University of Buea & The University of Bamenda.*

1 Introduction

The advent of globalisation and competitiveness in the business scene has pushed firms to resort for ways to increase performance and leverage on a high competitive edge (Akinnusi et al., 2017), as a result, special need should therefore be placed on retaining employees with diverse ages, experiences, knowledge, and backgrounds. Emmanuel and Dze (2021) emphasised that organisations in quest for performance have included workforce diversity as a determinant of organisational performance, the organisations believe a varied competence, skills and experience will offer a wide range of opportunities to explore (Emmanuel & Dze, 2021). Workforce diversity in organisations takes into consideration the differences that each employee brings into the organisation which serves as a strategic pillar with each employee's unique contribution to organisational competitiveness (Mor-Barak, 2015). Globally, workforce diversity seeks to capture the differences in individual employees in terms of their abilities and disabilities, race, gender, social class, religious inclination, age, ethnic, cultural background and sexual orientation has been a major challenge to most human resource departments in order to strike a balance between the differences and the high level performance expected by stakeholders.

According to Cho et al. (2017), Workforce diversity is defined as the presence of more than one feature among employees. From an organisational, perspective diversity is the presence of both commonalities and differences among its members in respect of gender, age, colour, culture, disability, and physical abilities. Thus it is thus expected that contemporary organisations will seek ways to improve on workforce diversity given that it yields; economic, intellectual, emotional and moral benefits to employees in particular and organisations as a whole (Saxena, 2014).

In the last 50 years, diversity has been approached from the legal perspective in countries like the US, where organisations were legally prohibited to show any form of discrimination to any person on any basis. This can be seen based on the contribution of Henry and Evans (2007) who emphasised that equal employment opportunity principle should be considered to ensure effective and efficient attainment of organisational goals rather than letting go bright people based on their differences. Furthermore, in the recent years, organisations have realised that workforce diversity is not just a legal issue, but a concept that must be embraced as a strategic tool for organisational success and sustainability (Bedi et al., 2014). According to Kyalo (2015), diversity management has proven to be able to create a positive change in performance and can significantly steer up new perspective and bring out fresh ideas for organisational survival (Bushardt et al., 2007). Workforce diversity is a complex phenomenon to manage and is often considered a prime source of challenge for human resource managers in contemporary organisations (Martín et al., 2013). Though challenging, most proactive organisations engage in it as an ethical and voluntary approach towards discrimination. Such organisations nurture inclusiveness, acknowledging the value of diversity, avoid losses associated to prejudice as well as criticisms or legal actions against the organisations (Devoe, 1999).

The unique nature of each individual in a diversified workforce exposes management to more problems at the workplace trying to nurture and transform the incompatibilities into outstanding individual and corporate performance (Martín et al., 2013). However, in order to have good employee performance, workforce diversity must be managed effectively both at the micro and macro levels in every institution. Phillips (2012) opines that, balanced gender diversity brings more balance to teams, thus creating less volatility and fewer conflicts. In Cameroon, racial diversity is not much of an issue, but ethnic diversity is a very big problem. In other countries such as USA and South Africa, there have been numerous reports of discrimination against blacks and other minor races (Shen et al., 2009). They are also less likely to get promoted and are usually assessed on a biased basis compared to men (Davison & Burke, 2000). Thus, gender inequality in an organisation results to loss in productivity in that it reduces their morale, self-esteem, and making it hard for the person to work effectively.

On the other hand, young people may lack the suitable experience that may be required in performing some duties and roles. With experience comes job knowledge: Job knowledge and experience have a direct impact on performance at work (Schmidt et al., 1986). Organisations therefore need to have a mix of all generations, in order to reap the benefits of a diverse and multigenerational workforce having a youthful exuberance, and mature employees with knowledge vast experience (Finn, 2015). Matz-Costa et al. (2012) describes age as a very visible type of diversity which gives almost instant rise to discrimination. Older employees have higher levels of company loyalty, better interpersonal skills, and better at teamwork. Stereotypes regarding younger workers includes that they have greater absenteeism and job-related accidents (Wessels, 2008). The diversity associated with demographics and the representations of the labour market are normal expectations in every establishment. Cameroon in general and the Universities of Buea and Bamenda cannot be an exception. The University of Buea was created in 1993 by Decree no 93/026 of 19 January as the first Anglo-Saxon state university. In December 2010, the University of Bamenda was created by Decree no. 2010/371 as the eight state university and second English speaking university. These two universities have the outstanding brand name as "the Anglo-Saxon state" universities in Cameroon. Being state entities, they are not only geared at providing education at a subsidised rate, but they are equally aimed at promoting state identity and unity. It's on the basis of this that the state regulations advocate for regional balance during recruitment of staff to work in all State Universities in Cameroon. In compliance to Equal Employment Opportunity obligations, these establishments are equally expected to be a miniature of the Cameroon labour market, as such having a blend of gender variation, age variation, language variation and others. The major factor of concern is attributed to unsatisfactory staff performance and the objective of the study is to what extent does workforce diversity management influence employees' performance in State Universities in Cameroon. The study then assumed that workforce diversity management significantly influences employees' performance in State Universities in Cameroon.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Empirical Review

Empirical studies have shown that workforce diversity plays a pivotal role on the performance of workforce as the study of Martins and Parsons (2007) indicates that there is a strong relationship between the two gender groups in attitude toward affirmative action. The researchers found an increased desire of both male and female employees to participate in diversity management initiatives and enhanced organisational attractiveness for employees. Patrick and Kumar (2012) found that there were significant differences between men and women professionals toward strategies for increasing awareness about workplace diversity. Women are more likely to work with a diverse teammate towards the achievement of goals. Also, the study of Muthiora (2014) found out that workforce diversity management such as education background, gender diversity, marital status and age diversity affect employee performance. The study concludes that education background, gender diversity, marital status and age diversity are critical workforce diversity management that determines employee performance in an organisation. In same line, Lang and Khatijah (2019) examined the effect of workforce diversity factors (generational diversity, gender diversity, ethnic/racial diversity and ethnic diversity) on organisational performance utilising secondary sources of data and finding revealed that, albeit the mixed results, most of the scholars found workforce diversity factors have a positive relationship with organisational performance.

Ndiang'ui (2013) identified the different diversity-management strategies adopted by the Florida public high school administrators and their influence on organisational performance. The researcher categorised diversity-management strategies into; non-compliant, compliant, reactive and proactive strategies. A survey instrument to 200 Florida public high school administrators' results from the inferential statistics did not show significant results. The lack of statistical significance in the inferential analysis, however, indicated that one cannot conclude that the type of diversity management strategy is significant in influencing the outcome of school performance. Kifordu and Ukpere (2014) determined whether workforce diversity has a relationship on customer related issues. The study employed a combination of secondary data, oral interview, and content analysis. A spearman's rank correlation coefficient of 0.95, revealing a positive influence of workforce diversity on organisational performance.

Odita and Egbule (2002) assessed the effects of workforce diversity on organisational effectiveness in Brewery industry using selected Brewery firms. Employing a linear regression and correlation analysis, findings showed that there is a significant positive relationship between the variables of workforce diversity and organisational effectiveness; in particular, cultural diversity was found to be more effective, also team building and group training-which mediates between workforce diversity and organisational effectiveness. Mande et al. (2018) established a relationship between gender diversity and employee performance of public universities in Western Kenya. The target population composed of four public universities and the respondents were 120 head of departments. The conclusions drawn from the study findings is that gender

diversity influences employee performance positively and majority of the employees are positive about gender diversity practices in public universities (Chrine et al., 2020).

Work force diversity is the systematic and planned commitment on the part of organisation to recruit and retain employees from diverse demographic backgrounds (Kirton & Greene, 2009). Kurowski and Gelfand (2002) state that managing diversity means varying the standard operating procedure, and it can result in more effective organisational systems. Kurowski and Gelfand (2002) equally suggest that in establishing organisational performance index, diversity should capture practices that involve understanding and appreciating interdependence of humanity, culture, and the natural environment. This in effect will lead to the tendency of practicing mutual respects for qualities and experiences that are different from that of each other. To them understanding that diversity includes not only ways of being but also ways of knowing, recognises that personal, cultural and institutionalized discrimination creates and sustains privileges for some, and at the same time creates and sustains disadvantages for others.

According to Dike (2013), primary basis of diversity includes; age, gender, sexual orientation, culture and many more) while secondary basis includes; income, religion, education and many more. According to Daft (2008), workforce diversity is the ability to achieve organisational success by using the best mix of the differences and similarities amongst workforce in terms of cultural background, age, race, physical abilities and disabilities, ethnicity, gender, religion and personality. In the view of Patrick and Kumar (2012) and Saxena (2014) these same variables account for a positive work environment. Bits of the views of these scholars have been adopted in the choice of the workforce diversity variables (age, gender and ethnicity) employed in this study.

Performance is how an employee performs a specific task within defined boundaries. Cascio (2000) defined performance as working effectively, which is the way somebody does a job, judged by its effectiveness. Additionally, to Huselid (1995) explains that organisational performance is affected by the performance of an individual employee, so the positive consequences of workforce diversity at the employee level would also go about as inherent and variables in developing employee cooperation. Academic staff performance is a critical aspect of higher education institutions, as it directly impacts students learning outcomes, research productivity, and institutional reputation (Ball, 2012). However, the literature on academic staff performance is fragmented for different aspects of performance including staff, research and service (Lam, 2013). Incorporating views gathered from these authors, the employees' performance in the universities in Cameroon will be measured using teaching hours and scientific publications.

2.2 Theoretical Review

Theoretically, the Equity Theory by John Stacy Adams (1963) formed the foundation on which this study is built. This theory seems to explain the need to maintain fairness and equity as essential ingredients to managerial practices within organisational context. An employee reflects on how much effort has expended and compares this to what has been

achieved from management to ensure equity. Additionally, this theory shows that employees strive to achieve equity between themselves and their co-workers in various aspects like duties, remuneration, punishments, benefits and others.

Also, The Human Capital Theory by Gary Becker (1964) seeks to explain that every employee has a set of skills and abilities which can be nurtured and improved through training and education. These abilities are numerous to which ethnic, gender, age peculiarities significantly contribute as they bring unique abilities. This theory provides a justification to the inclusion of age diversity which is a strategic element in organisational success as older age groups are more experienced, with a high sense of commitment to work and more, whereas the younger age group are more flexible in learning new things, adopting new technologies and developing new skills. A strategic mix of both age groups will propel employee performance within state universities as the case of this study.

The Trait Theory by Gordon Allport (1936) forms another basis on which this study anchors. This theory explains that dimensions of individual differences in tendencies to show consistent patterns of thoughts, feelings and actions (Costa & McCrae, 1990). Traits are said to be inherent and genetic in nature, such that those associated to males, cannot be found in females. This thus justifies the fact that both gender plays unique roles this is the premise behind this study.

Government policies

Government regulatory policies involve the implementation of rules by government actors, rules that are backed by the law (Brown & Jackson, 2022). Public policy can be generally defined as an institutionalised proposal to solve relevant and real world problems (Lassance, 2021). According to the National Assembly of Zambia and the Cabinet Handbook, a government policy can be used to describe any course of action, which intends to change a certain situation. The Handbook it is reiterated that policies must be thought of as a starting point for government to take a course of action that makes a real life change. Government uses policy to tackle a wide range of issues. Government can also change Law, so when a policy is created, it can be made to affect specific groups of people or everyone in our society.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Source: Author's Construction

The Figure 1 depicts the relationship between the dependent variable (Employee Performance) and the independent variable (Workforce diversity: Gender, Ethnic and Age Diversity). With the control variable (government policy), influencing the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. Dike (2013), primary basis of diversity includes; age, gender, sexual orientation, culture and many more) while secondary basis includes; income, religion, education and many. The relationship indicates that when gender diversity affects employee performance as if employees feel they are treated unfairly, this may intend affect their performance since they will be disloyal and disgruntled, also if employees feel their ethnic background fuels their ill treatment within an enterprise, they may feel unwanted and this may affect their contributions within their team and also build a wall of tension which may breed conflict, furthermore age diversity relates to employee performance in that if the employee feels that they are disrespected or discriminated based on being too young, young, old or too old, this may reduce the employee morale which greatly will affect their performance. However, though the above 3 factors have empirical relationship with employee performance, this study uses government policy as a control variable since all 3 variables are not just the only factors which will influence employee performance. Government policy from the framework will influence employee performance in that if the government decides to impose certain policies, to either favour a particular gender as the case of women inclusion policies, regional balance, this factors may influence employee performance.

3. Methodology

This study was restricted to the two state Anglo-Saxon universities in Cameroon: The University of Bamenda and University of Buea. The study adopted a causal and case study research designs. With the use of a questionnaire as a major instrument of data collection, primary data was sourced. The questionnaire was divided into three parts. Part A provided detail for demographic information about the respondent such as age group, years of experience, gender, and certificates achieved. Sections B used a five-point Likert scale to provide categorical statement associated to gender diversity management, ethnic background, ages of staff in their institution. Section C contained information related to the performance of staff captured in rate of absenteeism, employee engagement and participation, the number of hours taught. The questionnaire was pre-tested prior to being administered to the selected sample. The study conducted a pilot to check for validity and reliability of the questionnaire and also to ascertain the validity of diversity conflicts. An Alpha of Cronbach reliability test was carried out discover the consistency of the measurement and the results were satisfactory as seen below.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Standardized Items	N of Items
.768	.785	4

Table 1: Alpha of Cronbach

Source: Author's Construction

The target population for this study is made up of both administrative and academic staff from the University of Bamenda and University of Buea. The University of Bamenda and University of Buea has about 512 and 342 respectively, making a total of 854 Administrators for both Universities. A purposive sampling technique was employed given that the respondents are more connected to the category of persons that make the population than the researcher. A sample of 260 respondents was determined using the Krejcie-Morgan formula table. Though both universities are not of equal size or age, it was however equated to avoid some university results from being diluted by those of the higher proportion university.

Model Specification

A multiple linear regression model was used as specified below: The descriptive analysis was presented using both measures of central tendency and measures of dispersion (means and standard deviation, etc.). Furthermore, the inferential analysis was done using a multiple regression model specified for the study. The Statistical Package for Social Science was used to test whether all the predictor variables or only

a subset will be included in the fit. The prediction of EP was accomplished using the following equation:

Model without control variable

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 WFD_i + \mu$$

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \mu \dots \dots \dots [1]$$

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Gender_i + \beta_2 Ethnicity_i + \beta_3 Age_i + \mu \dots \dots \dots [2]$$

Model with control variable

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 X_{1i} + \beta_2 X_{2i} + \beta_3 X_{3i} + \beta_4 X_{4i} + \mu \dots \dots \dots [1c]$$

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Gender_i + \beta_2 Ethnicity_i + \beta_3 Age_i + \beta_4 Government Policy_i + \mu \dots \dots [2c]$$

Where, EP = Employee performance

WFD = Work Force Diversity (Gender, Ethnic and Age)

X₁ = Gender diversity

X₂ = Ethnic diversity

X₃ = Age diversity

X₄ = Government policy (control variable)

β₁, β₂, β₃, β₄ = regression coefficient of variables

β₀ = constant (coefficient of intercept).

4. Findings and Discussion

The questionnaire was distributed both online and hardcopies, given the technological knowhow of the target population. This was seen as the most appropriate means to reach out to the highly committed class of respondents under investigation. A period of three months was allowed for data collection at the end of this period, 260 treated responses were retained after discarding partially filled and inconsistent responses. This gave a response rate of 98.11% and the demographic information on respondents were gender, age range, work experience, and highest educational level.

Table 2: Demographic Information

Demographic variable	Frequency	Percentage %
Gender:		
Male	135	52
Female	125	48
Total	260	100
Age		
20 - 30 years	67	26
30 - 40 years	73	28
40 - 50 years	73	28
Above 50 years	47	18
Total	260	100
Work experience		
0 - 5 years	104	40
6 - 10 years	42	16
Above 10 years	114	44
Academic qualification		
Masters	88	34
Ph.D	104	40
Professors	36	14
Others	32	12

Source: Author's Construction

The results from Table 2 shows that; there were mostly constituted of males 135 (52%) than females 125 (48%) also the age distribution indicated that 67 (26%) of the respondents were between 20-30 years, followed by 73 (28%) between the ages 30-40 years and 40-50 years, while 47 (18%) were above 50 years. In essence, most of the administrators and lecturers sampled in this study were in their early youthful stage furthermore, with the work experience of the respondents, 104 (40%) have a work experience of 0-5 years indicating a young group, showing more job created at this level, 42 (16%) have a work experience of 6-10 years, meanwhile 114 (44%) have a work experience greater than 10 years. Finally, the academic qualification of respondents were 88 (34%) of the respondents, have master degree, followed by 104 (40%) with a Ph.D, 36 (14 %) were professors and 32 (12%) had other professional qualifications other than the classical; masters, PhD, Post doctorate. Given that the universities offer both classical and professional programmes, the mixture of qualifications provide a justification to the observed scenario.

Regression Analysis

H₀: workforce diversity significantly influence employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon.

In view of these hypotheses, the regression analysis was conducted to examine the influence of these variables (Gender Diversity, Ethnic Diversity, Age Diversity) on the dependent variable (Employee Performance). The result presented on Table 3 is the

influence of workforce diversity management on employee's performance without the control variable. The F-test was used to examine the general validity of the model. The results depict that the model is significant at 1% level of significance. We thus conclude that the model provides a better fit as presented on the Table 3. The alternative hypothesis can thus be accepted and confirm that workforce diversity management has a significant influence on employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon. The choose to include 2 tables; table 3 and 4 was to ascertain the effect of the control variable (government policy) on the overall results

Table 3: Regression Results of the Influence of Workforce Diversity on Employees' Performance in state universities in Cameroon

Model		Unstandardized		Standardize		
		Coefficients	Std. Error	Beta	T	Sig.
1	(Constant)	4.762	.211		22.600	.000
	Age Diversity	.122*	.027	.254	4.571	.000
	Gender Diversity	-.025	.031	-.044	-.795	.427
	Ethnic Diversity	-.302*	.040	-.416	-7.519	.000
	Durbin-Watson	1.709				
	R-Squared	.225				
	Adjusted R-Squared	.216				
	F-Statistics	24.793				
	Prob (F-Statistics)	.000 ^b				

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

* is 1% level of significance, Dependent Variable is Employees' Performance

Source: Field survey (2024)

As presented on Table 3, Age diversity and ethnic diversity from the result shows a significant influence on employee performance. However, Age diversity based on the above results has a positive standardized beta coefficient of 0.254 and a significant value of ($p= 0.000 < 1$), whereas though significant at 1%, ethnic diversity has a negative standardized beta coefficient of -0.416 meaning that when the differences with regards to ethnicity arises, it would lead to an inverse influence on employee performance. Finally, gender diversity has a negative and yet an insignificant influence ($B= -0.044$, $p= 0.427 > 1, 5$ and 10%), on employee performance in universities in Cameroon.

Table 3: Regression Results of the Influence of Workforce Diversity on Employees' Performance in state universities in Cameroon, Using Government Policy as a control variable

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Model		Unstandardized		Standardize		Sig.
		Coefficients		d		
		B	Std. Error	Beta	t	
1	(Constant)	2.764	.291		9.487	.000
	Age Diversity	.098*	.023	.204	4.163	.000
	Gender Diversity	-.014	.027	-.024	-.499	.618
	Ethnic Diversity	-.230*	.036	-.317	-6.387	.000
	Government Policy	.399*	.045	.441	8.869	.000
	Durbin-Watson	1.839				
	R-Squared	.408				
	Adjusted R-Squared	.399				
	F-Statistics	43.899				
	Prob(F-Statistics)	.000 ^b				

a. Dependent Variable: Employee Performance

* is 1% level of significance, Dependent Variable is Employees' Performance

Source: Field survey (2024)

As presented on Table 4, the result shows that the constant term has a beta value of 2.764 implying that employees' performance will be influenced by this degree even without workforce diversity where it showed a positive and significant result ($p = 0.000 < 1\%$). Age diversity and ethnic diversity from the result shows a significant influence on employee performance. However, Age diversity based on the above results has a positive standardized beta coefficient of 0.204 and a significant value of ($p = 0.000 < 1$). The findings indicating that age diversity has a significant effect on employee's performance in the university of Buea and Bamenda, this indicates that an employee's performance can be affected by the age diversity. As a result, we fail to reject the alternative hypothesis. This finding is in line with the results of Mande et al. (2018), age diversity influence employee performance positively and majority of the employees are positive about age diversity practices in public universities. age diversity management with respect to the regression analysis results revealed that age diversity management significantly influences employees' performance as the case, employees at different age groups are included in problem solving and decision making within the departments, ensured that employees are valued equally and fairly, and they are having the same opportunities to benefits like leaves, bonuses, and motivation. The literature backing to the obtained results is in line with other studies such as Muthiora (2014), Omotayo et al. (2020) and Nwahanye and Dze (2021). The study concludes that ethnic diversity, gender diversity, marital status and age diversity are critical workforce diversity management that determines employee performance in an organisation.

Though significant at 1%, ethnic diversity has a negative standardized beta coefficient of -0.317 meaning that when the differences with regards to ethnicity arise, it would lead to an inverse influence on employee performance. Additionally, ethnic diversity management on the other hand, the respondents agreed that employees in the

universities of Buea and Bamenda are assigned jobs and perform jobs flawlessly even when working with employees from different cultural inclinations. Also, the results further showed that ethnic diversity management and employee's performance is very significant these findings are in line with the findings of Muthiora (2014). The study found out that workforce diversity management such as education background, affect employee performance

Gender diversity has a negative and yet an insignificant influence ($B= 0.441$, $p= 0.618 > 1$, 5 and 10%), on employee performance in universities in Cameroon. The findings indicating that gender diversity has a significant effect on employee's performance in the university of Buea and Bamenda deviates from the findings of Chrine et al. (2020) who noted that gender diversity has a bearing on the administrators' performance, as the administrators work well together with the other gender. This collaboration ensures proper communication which such will lead to an upsurge in employee performance which has a pivotal role in organisation performance. This deviation may be as a result of the sectorial differences where the research was carried out, the four years difference or the nation and policies in force. Finally, the control variable government policy has a positive and significant p-value ($B= 0.399$, $p= 0.000 > 1\%$) which indicates that it could be considered a great contributor to employee performance.

From both tables, table 3 and 4 workforce diversity without the consideration of government policies has a 21.6% influence on employees' performance as represented by the adjusted R-squared value. The inclusion of government policies in the management of workforce diversity in state universities in Cameroon has a total influence of 39.9% on employees' performance. This thus implies that; government policies are highly beneficial when applied in the domain of workforce diversity in state universities in Cameroon, as it boosts the performance of university staff. Applying this finding to test the alternative hypothesis earlier stated, we thus fail to reject the alternative hypothesis and reaffirm that, workforce diversity management has a significant influence on employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon. It can therefore be inferred that 60.1% is accounted for by other variables not captured by this model. These possible uncaptured variables could be; qualification of staff, remuneration scheme, job design, workload, political instability (Anglophone crisis), infrastructural facilities, competitive nature of the higher education industry in Cameroon, working conditions and many others. The overall result is statistically significant at 1% level of significance, thus findings can be relied upon for policy recommendations.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, workforce diversity management, including gender, ethnicity and age has a significant influence on employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon. The literature reviewed in this study highlights the various benefits of a diverse workforce, including increased innovation, creativity, and productivity. However, it also acknowledges the challenges that come with managing a diverse workforce, such as potential conflicts and communication barriers should be watched out for.

The study's findings suggest that gender, ethnicity and age diversity are all important factors that influence employees' performance in state universities in Cameroon.

Specifically, the study found the gender diversity has a positive and insignificant influence employees' performance. This should not be mistaken to think that male and female counterparts should be given exactly the same roles and responsibilities. Given that they are fundamentally different in their social roles, this should be incorporated and ensure jobs are designed behaviourally to ensure the best is obtained from each gender. Ethnic diversity was also found to have a significant influence on performance, with employees from diverse ethnic backgrounds exhibiting collaborative and communication skills. Some collaborative research endeavours were highlighted which were only possible and outstanding because the diverse ethnic background of the researchers. Age diversity, however, had a significant influence on performance. Though experience and learning improves with longevity at work, one cannot deny the fact that young lecturers have a unique contribution in terms of strengths, fresh ideas, improved technological know-how and contemporary approaches to teaching that is tuned to fit the new generation students these universities host nowadays.

5.1. Recommendations

The study therefore recommends that, the Ministry of Higher Education should set up a supervisory organ that quarterly evaluates the extent to which each university meets the diversity goals. The Universities should be rated in line with prescribed standards and those that have shut fall be punished by reducing their state subventions. Also regular information and attendance sheets should be given to assess employees' performance

Furthermore, top administrators in all state universities in Cameroon should ensure that gender parity should be ensured in workforce composition. Each task force, each Department and each functional unit should ensure a blend of both male and female proportionate quotas to provide a psychologically balanced working climate with "unlike charges attracting each other." Also, the state communication channel: Cameroon Radio Television (CRTV) should have a programme that is specialised on handling issues plaguing the state Universities in Cameroon, with diversity being one of them and the sensitization on the importance of diversity management. Ethnic diversity should be ensured by making sure each state university have a minimum and ceiling proportion of staff from all the ethnic groups found in Cameroon. Additionally, to should cut across the different strategic business units and service centres of the University. The age compositions in all department should be varied and standardized across various departments or service centres. More importantly, the age compositions should reflect that of the labour market.

5.2. Suggestion for further studies

Additional findings on related areas can provide a boost to the findings of this study. Possible avenues for related research include;

- A comparative analysis of workforce diversity management for state universities in French Speaking and English Speaking universities in Cameroon.
- Also, a comparative analysis of workforce diversity management influence in state universities as oppose to private universities in Cameroon.

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